

Special Relativistic Equivalence of Fermat's Least Time Principle and Least Action

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 11, 2026

In (1), an argument is presented linking index of refraction, photons and Fermat's Least Time Principle to Least Action. We try to create the same equivalence based on the notions of special relativity. We do not consider an index of refraction or photons.

We argue that special relativity yields the notions of E (energy), p (momentum) and also describes x and t . Physically, Newton knew about these entities and linked them to force, i.e. the notion of push or pull. Given that full expressions for E, p arise from special relativity, we suggest that linear derivatives in t, x of E, p may be linked to the notion of force. In particular, we suggest that a compressed spring is in a particular physical state which we call an energy state. We argue that one should be able to equate dE from special relativity to Fdx based on this idea. One must then find an expression for F (based on p, E and a trial test of d/dt or d/dx). As is well-known, $F=dp/dt$ is a solution.

Given $F = dp/dt$, it is well-known that this equation follows from Lagrangian theory. In particular, there exists a function $L(v, x, t)$ such that dL/dv partial = p . If one create the classical action: $\int_{(t_1, t_2)} dt L(x, v, t)$, then a variation of this leads to: $d/dt dL/dv$ partial - $dL/dx=0$ which is equivalent to $dp/dt = F$. The Lagrangian approach is a variational approach. Fermat's Least Time Principle (often used to derive Snell's Law) is also a variation strategy. In (1), it is stated that the two are equivalent. We wish to examine this idea through special relativity.

Special relativity uses the variables x, t, E, p and so we consider dL/dv partial = $dL/d(x/t) = p$ and consider varying with respect to x with t a constant for free motion. Then:

$d/dx (Lt) = p$ or $Lt = px + \text{function}(E, p, t)$. In such a case, dx is a variation which may occur in x at t . This is the notion that occurs when one varies the action, except that we apply it to dL/dv partial. One may note the existence of a Lorentz invariant: $-Et+px$. A second feature of Lagrangian theory is that Hamiltonian often= $E = pv - L$. Testing with the Lorentz invariant: $pv-L = px/t + E - pv = E$. The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ is a solution for Lt , the classical action.

To see that one is actually minimizing follows from holding t constant in $d/d(x/t)$ and consider dx , i.e. to possible x values. Given $-Et+px$, minimizing this function and treating x and t independently means that $-Et$ should be minimized and px also, but separately. For Snell's law, E is the same in n_1, n_2 (indices of refraction) and so one minimizes t . Now $t = x / (c/n) = nx/c$, but $p_i = n_i p$ (where p is the photon momentum in a vacuum). Minimizing time is the same as minimizing nx or equivalently, px .

The fact that one considers t and x as independent in $-Et+px$ suggests that one considers separate fluctuations in t and x (aside from $x=vt$). These fluctuations leave $-Et+px$ unchanged if $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$. This leads to the idea of free particle quantum mechanics, but we argue that by considering $Lt = -Et+px$, one is already making use of the idea of a dx independent of t and that this idea already anticipates free particle quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity and the Notion of E and p

Even though Newton introduced the ideas of kinetic energy and momentum (mv), full expressions for these follow from special relativity:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((1))$$

At first, one might consider these as transformations of $m_0 c^2$ in a rest frame. Physically, they must be associated with force as it is force (a push or pull) which moves m_0 (even if it is seen to move due to a moving frame). Momentum p is a vector in the direction of the force, so one might ask: What is m_0 ? In Newton's view, m_0 is linked with an inertial force, i.e. a force is required to move m_0 , but this force can be applied in any direction. m_0 seems to be a state property of a particle (with rest mass) and is independent of the direction of the force. This state property changes to E when the particle moves, but is still a number.

Consider next a physical spring. When it is squeezed, force is applied over distance to create a state of the spring. One might as a result suggest that this state is linked with

$$\int F dx \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{or } \int F \cdot dr)$$

If a particle at rest (m_0) is placed next to the squeezed spring, then when the spring is released (with one end fixed), the particle will move and reach a velocity v . Different m_0 values lead to different v values. Given that one $((2))$ is a number, one might suggest that the moving particle should be represented by a state variable which is also a number, not a vector. This leads to the possible choice of E from $((1))$.

If that is the case:

$$dE = F dx \quad ((3))$$

For m_0 constant, $dE = dE/dv dv$. One might ask: What is a solution for F ? It is well-known that:

$$dp/dt = F \quad \text{is a solution} \quad ((4))$$

$$dE = m_0 c^2 v dv / (1 - v^2/c^2)^{3/2} \quad \text{and} \quad dp \cdot v = m_0 v / (1 - v^2/c^2)^{3/2} (dv (1 - v^2/c^2) + v dv) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, $dp/dt = F$ may be established from special relativity.

Lagrangian Theory and Variation of an Action

Lagrangian theory has the goal of reproducing $((4))$. It states that there is a Lagrangian function $L(x, t, v)$ such that:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad H = \text{energy (often)} = pv - L \quad ((5b))$$

Given that p is a relativistic variable, we suggest that one should consider L in terms of special relativity.

As a first approach, one may note that a solution is:

$$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((6))$$

This may formally be shown to be equivalent to $(-Et+px)/t$ which is a Lorentz invariant if one sets $x=vt$. In other words:

$$-Et+px = Lt \quad ((7))$$

Another way to achieve this result is more revealing. Given that:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p, \quad ((8))$$

we suggest that one write ((8)) in terms of special relativistic variables x, t, E, p for a free particle. This leads to a problem because:

$$v=x/t \quad ((9))$$

If one varies v , in principle one might change x and t . We suggest holding t constant and considering two possible x points, which is what happens in the variation of the classical action. Then:

$$t \, dL/dx = p \quad \text{or} \quad tL = px + \text{function}(t, p, E) \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{If one insists on ((5b)), then } L = -Et+px \quad ((11))$$

We stress that in this approach, the idea of a variation in x independent of t has been made. By symmetry, one should consider a change in t independent of x . One no longer considers

$x=vt$ ((12)) with these fluctuations in x, t , but ((12)) is still consistent with the entire special relativistic framework

One considers fluctuations in x and t which are linked with the motion $x=vt$. From $-Et+px$

$$dt = \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and leave } -Et+px \text{ unchanged} \quad ((13))$$

We note that in this approach $L = -E+px/t$. In general, one should not change x , but v , but if independent x, t fluctuations are allowed then one may write $t \, dL/dx \text{ partial} = p$, with the understanding that E and p are linked to the fluctuations and that overall one has $x=vt$. We suggest that this idea ((13)) leads to free particle quantum mechanics, but shows that the deterministic $x=vt$ is also present, i.e. there is a duality.

Fermat's Least Time Principle

We have suggested that $-Et+px = Lt$ and so it may be varied (minimized). This is done by considering independent fluctuations in x and t . Given this idea, one may minimize Et or px separately. In a Snell's law problem

E is the same in n_1 and n_2 (indices of refraction) ((14))

One minimizes time t .

If one chose to minimize px instead, one may note that $p_i = n_i p$, where p is the momentum in a vacuum and $x = c/n_i t$.

Minimizing time is the same as minimizing: $x \cdot n_i = x \cdot p$ ((15))

Thus, minimization of the free particle classical action, $-Et+px$ (independent x, t fluctuations) is equivalent to Fermat's least Et principle.

The Meaning of Delta x in the Variation of the Classical Action

A free particle moves as $x=vt$. In such a case, one has dx and dt pieces such that $dx=v dt$. Variation of the classical action, however, considers a $\delta x(t)$ at t which shifts x from its $x=vt$ value. This is the idea of $\delta x(t)$ in the classical action variation. We suggest that this kind of variation also has meaning in $-Et+px = Lt = -t m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. One may consider a fixed t and vary x in $-Et+px$. This leads to a kind of strange derivative dL/dx partial, but also shows a physical δx , independent of a δt . We suggest that for $\delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\delta x = \hbar/p$, $-Et+px$ remains constant and that one introduces free particle quantum mechanics. Thus, we suggest that the idea of varying δx , is already linked to the δx in $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest, however, that physically δx means that the particle may interact within a δx range as in 2-slit interference.

Conclusion

We try to understand how the notion of E, p, x, t and $F=dp/dt$ arise from special relativity. Next, we consider obtaining a free particle special relativistic Lagrangian. The Lagrangian $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ is a solution, but it is not written in terms of special relativistic variables E, p, x, t . One may write $v=x/t$, but E and p are still missing. Bringing then in yields $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \cdot t = -Et+px$. If one wishes to use dL/dv partial in terms of special relativistic variables, then $v=x/t$, but one may only vary one. If one chooses to vary x , then one is considering independent x, t fluctuations which are separate from $x=vt$, yet $x=vt$ still holds as a separate equation. This suggests that $t dL/dx$ partial = p or $tL = px + \text{function}(t, p, E)$. Using $E=pv-L$ yields $Lt = -Et+px$. The notion of independent x, t fluctuations leads to free particle quantum mechanics, Varying t and x separately means that Et minimization is equivalent to px minimization which we show is equivalent to Fermat's Least Time (really Least Et) principle.

References

1. Anderson et al Fermat's Principle and Hamilton's Principle: Does a least action take a least time happening? (2020)
<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1467/1/012038/pdf>